

Constraining the Reliability of the Lunar Ice Detection with M³ Data

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Introduction:

Permanently shadowed regions (PSRs) of the Moon were suggested to act as cold traps for volatiles, due to their extremely low temperatures (<110 K) [1,2]. Water ice in the lunar cold traps may have different origins, both endogenous and exogenous [3,4].

PSRs receive no direct sunlight; however, secondary illumination makes it possible to observe their interiors, although this is challenging due to the complex geometry, multiple scattering effects, and the resulting very low signal [5].

Several spacecraft have studied the lunar poles over the past thirty years using different instruments [6-9], but no unambiguous evidence of the presence of water ice has been found.

The Moon Mineralogy Mapper (M³) spectral analysis [10], revealed absorptions of water ice at about 1.25, 1.5, and 2.0 μm in several permanently shadowed craters at both lunar poles. However, latest results based on radiance contrast, obtained by Danuri ShadowCam, [11-13] show that the ice-bearing areas identified by M³ exhibit no significant brightness contrast relative to their surroundings, posing the question about the presence of ice in the immediate subsurface.

Aim of this work:

We analyzed the M³ spectral data to better characterize the abundance and spatial distribution of water ice, which are of critical importance for future in situ robotic investigations and human explorations.

We performed a detailed analysis using a selection method similar to the one applied by Li et al [10]. We identified unexpected water ice signatures in areas where ice is not expected to be stable (non-PSRs). Given that, we investigated the possible source of such ice-like features in the M³ spectra, including a possible non-linearity in the instrument response for extremely low level of signal, as those in PSRs and in shadows.

Methods:

To find water ice, we applied a procedure based on the identification of the 1.25, 1.5 and 2.0 μm absorption bands. To confirm the robustness of the water ice detections we applied the same procedure in non-PSR regions (between 69° S to 75° S latitude), that are not expected to contain water ice. Moreover, since we are dealing with very low signal data slightly higher, and sometimes even lower, than the dark signal, we evaluated the linearity of the instrument in these low signal pixels. Finally, we used a statistical approach to assess whether the percentage of ice

detections in the M³ data represents true detections or false positives induced by noise and non-linearity.

Results:

Figure 1 shows the mean spectra of the detected pixels in a South Pole Region of Interest (SP ROI, fig. 1a) containing a PSR and in a region, 69° S - 75° S (fig. 1b), where water ice is not expected to be present [14]. Figure 1c and 1d shows the detected pixels distribution in the SP ROI and in the lower latitude region. The detection of the same spectral features in both regions raises serious concerns about the reliability of these signatures. Moreover, the detections are often distributed along a same detector sample, indicating a correlation with instrumental behavior rather than with localized surface features. Taken together, these results imply that the apparent detection of water ice at the South Pole is likely driven by data artifacts or systematic effects, rather than an actual surface ice deposit.

Figure 1: Mean spectra of the detected pixels are shown in figure (a, b) for the SP ROI and the lower latitude region 69° S - 75° S, respectively. The spectra are normalized to their mean value. Vertical dashed lines in the mean spectra indicate the 1250, 1500 and 2000 nm absorption band positions of water ice [15]. Positive detections (yellow dots) distribution in the SP ROI and in the lower latitude region are shown in panels c and d respectively.

We conducted a linearity analysis of the data and found that the spectra become distorted when going from high to low radiances. The shape of the distortion is very similar to the Radiance Calibration Coef-

ficient (RCC) used for the calibration of the instrument.

Then, we applied a statistical analysis to evaluate whether random noise, combined with the instrument's non-linear spectral response, can explain all apparent water ice detections. We obtained a simulated dataset by using the non linear shape found in the linearity analysis and injecting the M^3 noise through a MonteCarlo simulations. Figure 2 shows the scatterplot between the number of water ice detections in both the simulated and the M^3 datasets for different reflectance bins.

Figure 1: Detections in simulated and original datasets.

The strong linear anticorrelation between the number of detections in both datasets and reflectance provides definitive evidence that the water ice spectral signatures observed in the M^3 data are induced by instrumental non-linearity rather than by the presence of surface water ice.

Conclusions:

In conclusion, we found that water ice-like signatures can be found in M^3 data in regions where ice is not expected to be stable. This detections were shown to be due to the combination of the nonlinear instrumental response and low signal-to-noise ratio of the data. However, this work does not argue against the presence of surface or sub-surface water ice in lunar PSRs, but it points out that the M^3 data are affected by instrumental issues that can significantly bias the detection of water ice signatures at very low signal levels. Future in situ investigations of the lunar poles will be crucial for determining whether water ice is present, by enabling the combination of multiple complementary datasets, higher signal-to-noise measurements, and instruments specifically designed to operate in extremely low-illumination environments.

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